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Effects of Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy on Performance in Reading Comprehension Among Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated effects of peer tutoring instructional strategy on performance in reading comprehension among secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives, with corresponding research questions and hypotheses, respectively. The study adopted pre- test post- test quasi- experimental research design. The population for this study comprised of 19, 282 senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Bayelsa State. A simple random sampling and stratified random sampling techniques were used to select size of 100 students from the target population. The instrument used for data collection was Reading Comprehension Performance Test (RCPT) which was used to determine the academic performance of the students. In establishing the reliability of the instrument, kuder Richardson (K-R 21) formula was employed and a reliability coefficient of 0.72 was obtained. A pre- test of Reading Comprehension Performance Test (RCPT) was given to all the students before the treatment. Thereafter, the experimental group was subjected to treatment. Data analysis was subjected to Mean Scores, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that peer tutoring learning technique is more effective than discussion method. Based on the findings, it was recommended that teachers at all levels should be conversant with the new learning techniques. This will enable them to vary their mode of presenting their lessons to the students.

Keywords: English Language, Peer Tutoring, Reading Comprehension, Teaching Technique and Discussion Method.

Introduction

English language as major subject in the school curriculum and as an official language in Nigeria needs to be given proper attention particularly in content delivery. English language as an official language in Nigeria refers to a language selected by a bilingual or multilingual country to serve a wide range of function, for example, Education, as a medium of government business, media, and high level of commerce and so on. In terms of education, it calls for proper teaching techniques which will help equip students with the potentiality, as well as push them for deeper understanding of the subject (ijoko, 2021).

English language from the researcher's point of view requires a method which will help the teacher to use the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing. English language learners in particular, may thrive in a peer tutoring learning environment because they will have the opportunity to learn with others through peer-to-peer exchange, to develop their academic vocabularies through dialogue, to use their own strengths and cultural backgrounds, and to accelerate their language acquisition at the same time as they are learning about topics of interest. Peer tutoring learning requires the production of authentic (oral and written) language.

Wikipedia (2015) defined Peer tutoring as a teaching strategy in which students are paired together to practice academic skills and master content. Teachers may use peer tutoring to help accommodate a classroom full of diverse students who need more individual attention. There are a variety of factors teachers should be aware of when planning a peer tutoring lesson. Different schools, classrooms, and teachers are able to provide different types of resources and expertise to contribute to the success of a peer tutoring program. Keep in mind, the strategies described in this lesson will not work in every situation with every student all the time. It is up to you as the teacher to assess these strategies and see what will work for your specific population of students. Peer tutoring is meant to be a flexible and adaptable teaching method, which should allow for some trial and error as you shape your individual programs.

Peer tutor partnerships may be designed in a few different ways. Teachers may assign some of their higher achieving students to work with peers in the classroom who are struggling, or they could assign students with similar

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abilities to work together, each taking turns being the tutor and the tutee. They may also work with other teachers to pair up older students who have mastered the content with younger students who are being introduced to something new, which is known as cross-age tutoring.

In Nigeria, however due to technological development, reading habits are changing. In our society today, while technology is slowly taking a steady control over individual lives, the reading habit is fast vanishing into the thin air. Students now lack the skill of reading; instead they spend more time or hours on electronic media. Browsing the net, playing with handsets seem to be the order of the day, thereby making reading a book or any other piece of written material in a quiet and peaceful corner of a library or a home, an old fashioned idea. Students are hardly interested in reading for pleasure and enjoyment instead, they read to pass examination. The declining interest in reading culture among out pupils/students is a cause for alarm and a challenge to all. Something needs to be done to lessen this problem.

Consequent upon the observation on student's inability to demonstrate proficiency in English Language, this has mostly been attributed to their inability to read passages with comprehension. This research will take interest in instructional methodology of reading comprehension. Reading with understanding is one of the most important ways to achieve academic advancement of any individual irrespective of the individual's discipline. But research has indicated that not enough attention has been given to reading instruction and even when it is given, the teacher dominates the class. Adeniyi and Oladunjoye, (2009) as cited by Oyetunde (2012) observed that reading comprehension instruction therefore deserves more attention than it is currently receiving. Student centered approaches are being advocated for the contemporary classroom; the need to expose learners to strategies which will involve their active participation in the learning environment informed the choice of these strategies. Similarly, Adeniyi and Oladunjoye (2009) as cited by Okafor (2016) stated that the instructional technique employed by the teachers' of English language, sex of the students may as well influence students' performance in reading comprehension.

The concept of reading comprehension is one that has evoked varied definitions by different scholars. Herring (2014) described reading as a process of interaction between the writer of a text and the reader who is trying to make meaning out of what the author of the text has encoded. They further explained that reading involves information gathering which the reader seeks to improve his/her knowledge base and become aware of the world around him/her. They identified four stages of efficient reading, namely: recognition, comprehension, retention and recall. These stages involve the reader's ability to recognize meaning of words as used in the text, grasp the author's message, store information extracted from the text in the memory and also remember what has been read. Rudestum (2014) describe reading as a specialized and complex skill involving other skills. He further stated that the ability to read requires the reader to develop the following skills; learning to read in various ways for example skimming and scanning.

Adapting the way they read according to the text and their reason for reading; reading "actively"-using a dictionary, guessing or asking for an unknown word; understanding the relationship between sentences; helping understanding by using textual and visual clues i.e., headings, the way the text is organized into paragraph punctuation, signal words, pictures, typography etc using textual clues where the learners understand, what they and other people are doing at the time. Inferring meaning, guessing meaning and background knowledge of the culture about which they are reading.

Chukueggu and Umara- Okeke (2013) agreed that reading skill includes the following components: Knowledge of the language to be read, ability to separate spoken words into component sounds, ability to discriminate the letters of the alphabet, understanding of the principle of reading from left to right, right to left and ability to comprehend a text. They saw reading comprehension as the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language. Extracting meaning from the text is to understand what the author has explicitly or implicitly stated. Reading undeniably involves two necessary elements: reader and a text. It also recognizes a third element which is equally influential in reading namely the writer. The text is processed by the reader in an interaction of the reader and the text and equally, plausibly, the reader and the writer. Snow argued that, texts do not have unitary meanings potentially accessible to all but rather allow for variety in interpretation by different readers, governed by factors such as purpose, background knowledge and the writer in the act of reading. They thus see reading as cooperation and negotiation. Reading lessons should aim at facilitating acquisition and development of enduring, whole literacy skills needed for communication in different contexts.

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There is also no consensus on what constitutes acceptable practices and methods of reading. However current reading research point to a shift towards meaning oriented reading consisting of understanding of whole and authentic texts. Reading has been viewed within the cognitive psychology as an activity in which participants construct meaning by integrating their previous or existing knowledge with the new knowledge in the text. Boardman (2008) as cited by Chukueggu and Umara- Okeke (2013) stated that the goal of reading comprehension instruction is to help students understand written language. Students, who comprehend well, monitor their understanding as they read and use fix-up strategies, such as re-reading or summarizing, when understanding breaks down. Self-monitoring also helps students relate new information to their prior knowledge, fostering better understanding.

Comprehension is at the centre of reading. Collins and Cheek (2014) describe reading as a process that requires the use of complex thought processes to interpret printed symbols as meaningful units and comprehend them as a thought unit in order to understand a printed text. Reading as a learning process is indispensable in the development of other language skills. As important as reading is, research still shows that majority of Nigerian students in the secondary school possesses poor reading ability. Such students understand little of written texts and thus are unable to analyze and interpret them. Adams, (2019) stated that skilled comprehension readers employ a number of cognitive skills. In the higher level skill process, the reader relates reading to existing knowledge and creates inferential bridge between things that are written and things that are previously experienced. The lower level cognitive processes involve recognition of letters and words and automatic activation of word meanings during the reading. Thus, skilled reading largely depends upon thorough familiarity with individual letters and words and frequent patterns to enable words flow effortlessly from print to meaning (Adam, 2019).

Performance of students in reading comprehension can also be influenced by gender. Gender is a social phenomenon with an important pedagogical implication in second language learning. Many researchers have shown that females perform better than males in verbal tasks in school works. This study therefore believes that apart from instructional strategy of the teacher, sex of students may influence students' achievement in English Language reading comprehension. This method of teaching is based upon active participation of every member of the class in a collective exploration and public evaluation of ideas. Usually, there is no restraint to self-expression as members' pool ideas in co-operative task of understanding an issue and learning from each other. Discussion could serve as a follow-up to a lecture, a mid-course examination of ideas or a recapitulation session (Achuoneye & Ajoku, 2019).

The discussion method makes itself amenable to the teaching of variety of contents in diverse subject area. Arrangement could be concluded for the entire class to participate in a discussion; the class can also be divided into small groups. It is also possible to arrange for panel discussion. The discussion provides for students' involvement, which in turn helps to stimulate and reinforce learning. Discussion method of teaching involves communication of ideas, facts, and opinions by group of learners on an identified and clearly stated instructional objective using skills as speaking, listening and non-verbal processes. For better students' participation, a group size of 5 to 10 members is considered manageable. In the group, both the participants and the moderator (usually the teacher) pull their knowledge together to understand and appreciate a problem by learning from one another. Each member of the group is assigned a specific time limit to address the group while other members listen and observe.

The success and effectiveness of the method depends upon how well the learners are prepared and motivated to participate and the sensitivity of the teacher to the spontaneity of the participants. Thus, the method demands adequate preparation on the part of the teacher (or the conference leader) and participants. Two key points should be noted, Discussion requires a clearly stated objective to serve as a focus and guiding post. Neglecting the criterion may hamper the realisation of the set objectives as discussion may degenerate to mere informal debate on superficial issues and the emergence of a star speaker who eventually will dominate the discussion. Secondly, to ensure effective participation of the members, prior knowledge of the discussion topic is essential. The discussion topic could be derived from several controlled experiences of the learners such as going on a field trip, viewing an educational film, listening to a lecture or reading as assigned book.

The subtle art of controlling the discussion to realise fully the gains is the responsibility of the teacher or the director. Foremost, the teacher must understand the purpose of the discussion method. Every member of the group should be free to contribute. This implies that there should not be rigid rules as to restrain free exchange of ideas. Potentially dominant personalities must not be allowed to take over the discussion and the naturally reticent must be encouraged to contribute (Curson as cited in Ogwu, 2016). The teacher must skillfully perform this duty without

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offending anyone. Simultaneously, he should create an environment capable of rewarding each participant for his contribution.

Statement of the Research Problem

Poor performance in English Language at the secondary and even tertiary levels is an issue of concern in the Nigeria educational system. The most noticeable indication of under- performance is in the WAEC conducted SSCE English examination (Ijoko, 2021). The WAEC chief examiners’ report each year confirms this. In 2022 the report stated that: “This paper was well within the experience of the candidates and the standard in the previous years; the candidates’ performance however was generally disappointing. The above assertion has remained a source of great concern to students, teachers, parents and government. The percentage passes in examination like WAEC, NECO, and GCE continue to decline despite increasing efforts by government to stem the trend. The poor state of learning reading comprehension in our schools has been attributed to many factors. Among the factors that may have accounted for poor performance in the subject are: quality of teaching techniques employed by the teachers, lack of knowledge of subject- matter, lack of interest and other students’ related factors. In fact, many teachers of language in Nigeria are not aware of the current methods or principles of second language teaching (Oyetunde as cited in Ijoko, 2021). Experts have called for the use of instructional techniques that are student- center and participatory in nature, which will enable the learners take ownership of learning in group context. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate effects of peer tutoring instructional strategy on performance in reading comprehension among secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate effects of peer tutoring instructional strategy on performance in reading comprehension among secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. compare the difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method.
2. examine whether there is a difference in the mean performances scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. what is the difference in mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method?
2. what is the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method.
- H₀₂. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique.

Methodology

The study adopted the pre-test post-test quasi- experimental research design. The population of the study comprised all the SS 2 students in the 297 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The population of SS 2 students for the 2023/2024 academic session 19,282 students (Source: Bayelsa State Post Primary Schools Board, office of the Directorate of Inspection and Statistics, 2024). A sample size of 100 SS 2 students was used for this study. A simple random sampling and stratified random sampling techniques were used to compose the sample. Simple random sampling was used to draw one (1) local government area from the eight (8) of them in the state. It was done by writing out the names of the eight (8) local government areas on a piece of paper. The 8 pieces of paper bearing the respective names of the local government areas were thoroughly shuffled in a container and one (1) of it was randomly drawn without replacement. After drawing the one (1) local government area by simple random sampling, a disproportionate stratified random sampling was used to draw a number of schools from the educational zones in the local government

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area for the study. Twenty (20) items multiple choice test entitled “Reading Comprehension Performance Test” (RCPT) was used in this research to determine students’ academic performance. The face and content validity of the instrument was validated by the researcher’s supervisor and two experts in the Department of Curriculum Studies and Instructional Technology, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The opinions of English Language experts were sought. The instrument was modified based on the suggestions of these experts before administration. The mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: what is the difference in mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method?

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation, and mean gain of students’ performance in reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and discussion method

Method	Pre- test			Post – test		Actual Score
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Peer tutoring technique	50	43.90	11.08	85.60	8.18	41.70
Discussion Method	50	40.40	7.75	63.20	6.91	22.80

Table 1 showed that students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique had a mean score and a standard deviation of 43.90 and 11.08 during the pre-test while students that were taught reading comprehension using discussion method had a mean and standard deviation 40.40 and 7.75. After post-test, students taught with Peer tutoring technique had a mean score of 85.60 and standard deviation of 8.18 while those taught using discussion method had a mean score of 63.20 and standard deviation of 6.91. The mean gain for students taught with Peer tutoring technique was 41.70 while students taught using discussion method was 22.80. This indicated that students taught with peer tutoring technique performed better than the students taught with discussion method.

Research Question 2: what is the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique?

Table 2: Mean, standard deviation, and Mean gain of male and female students’ taught reading comprehension using Peer tutoring strategy.

Gender	Pre- test			Post – test		Actual Score
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	22	43.80	10.73	85.00	9.13	41.20
Female	28	44.00	11.64	86.20	7.26	42.20

Table 2 showed the analysis of male and female students’ performance taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique. Male students taught with peer tutoring learning technique at the pre-test had the mean score of 43.80 and standard deviation of 10.73 while female students exposed to peer tutoring learning technique had the mean score of 44.00 and standard deviation of 11.64. Male students taught with peer tutoring learning technique at post-test had the mean score of 85.00 and standard deviation of 9.13 with mean gain of 41.20, while female students exposed to peer tutoring learning technique had the mean score of 86.20 and standard deviation of 7.26 with mean gain of 42.20. This indicated that the difference was in favour of female students.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA of students’ performance based on methods

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
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Corrected Model	12551.317 ^a	2	6275.659	108.458	.000	.691
Intercept	27433.504	1	27433.504	474.114	.000	.830
Pretest	7.317	1	7.317	.126	.723	.001
Methods	12237.845	1	12237.845	211.498	.000	.686
Error	5612.683	97	57.863			
Total	571700.000	100				
Corrected Total	18164.000	99				

Table 3 showed that the analysis of covariance in the performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those taught using the discussion method yielded an F (1,97) of 211.498 with associated exact probability value of 0.001. Since the associated probability (0.001) was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension with Peer Tutoring Learning Technique and those taught with Discussion Method.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA of students' performance based on gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	78.862 ^a	2	39.431	.579	.565	.024
Intercept	19358.850	1	19358.850	284.055	.000	.858
Pretest	60.862	1	60.862	.893	.349	.019
Gender	17.400	1	17.400	.255	.616	.005
Error	3203.138	47	68.152			
Total	369650.000	50				
Corrected Total	3282.000	49				

Table 4 showed that the analysis of covariance in the performance mean scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique yielded an F (1,47) of 0.590 with associated exact probability value of 0.446. Since the associated probability (0.446) was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there was no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique

Discussion of Findings

Students' Performance in Reading Comprehension Using Peer Tutoring Learning Technique and Discussion Method

Findings from table 1 revealed a significant difference between the performances of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and discussion method which is in favour of peer tutoring learning technique. This result indicates that the Peer Tutoring learning technique is more effective in enhancing of students' performance than the discussion method in reading comprehension. This is in line with the findings of Rahman et al., (2018), Akpana and Oludo (2019) and Abduraheem (2017) who found that Peer Tutoring learning technique have positive effect on students' performance. The effectiveness could be that students were actively involved in learning process and were able to find out some information for themselves through activity-based instructional strategy such as peer tutoring instructional method and teaching technique therefore, knowledge is better facilitated.

Male and Female Students' Performance in Reading Comprehension Using Peer Tutoring Learning Technique

In table 2 the study revealed that male students differed from the female students on their mean performance scores in reading comprehension. This observed difference is in favour of female students in peer-tutoring learning technique group. Table 4 revealed that gender has no significant effect on student performance in reading comprehension. Thus male and female students differ in their academic performance in reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique was not significant. This finding implies that whether a student is male or female,

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gender does not make a difference in their academic performance. This is in line with the findings of Ajai and Imoku (2015) and Akpana and Oludo (2019). The finding reveals as well that academic performance gained by female surpassed that of their male counterpart. This study therefore asserts that students' academic performance is not a function of gender.

Conclusions

Reading is one of the basic language skills that aid people to learn, communicate and express ideas effectively. It is not developed naturally but by proper teaching and studying through a range of activities and tasks. Teachers of English language in secondary schools should be able to help the learners by teaching them various steps involved in effective reading comprehension. It is the duty of the teacher to lead the learners to read, understand the reading passage by analysing the rudiments found in the passage such as: grammar, idioms, figurative expression, etc. Therefore, the present study is an effort to improve reading comprehension.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Peer tutoring learning technique are effective in improving students' performance in reading comprehension. Therefore, emphasis should be given to equipping students with the necessary skills in using the techniques.
2. The male students should as well be given more attention in the development of their reading comprehension skills by encouraging them to take more roles in the activities of literature circles in reading comprehension while the female students should be encouraged with incentives for best performance so as to balance the performance level in the class.

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